

From Gut to Mind: The Link Between Inflammatory Bowel Disease and Mood Disorders

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Abstract

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), such as Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), has traditionally been recognized as being solely a gastrointestinal illness. However, there is increasing evidence that IBD is not just gut disease but also involves significant neuropsychiatric manifestations [1,2]. This review overviews the complex interaction between IBD and mood disorders of anxiety and depression within the context of the gut-brain axis [3]. The literature consistently reveals greater prevalence rates of mood disorders in IBD patients compared with healthy controls [4,5], with varied clinical correlates of UC and CD [6]. Perhaps most relevantly, however, this association is bidirectional rather than reactive [7,8], as each condition is capable of worsening the other by way of various neurobiologic mechanisms. A number of mechanisms have been implicated connecting gut illness with mood dysregulation in IBD, such as microbiota modulation of neurotransmitter accessibility and integrity of the blood-brain barrier [9,10], immune-mediated pathways through inflammatory cytokines and altered tryptophan metabolism [11,12], and neural circuitry through vagal nerve and enteric nervous system impairment [13]. These mechanisms not only account for the common high rate of anxiety and depression in IBD but also outline the pathways along which psychological distress may influence disease onset, exacerbation, and clinical outcome. It has significant implications for the understanding of the entire spectrum of presentations of IBD and in formulating more integrative care strategies for the patient [14,15].

1. Introduction

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is a group of chronic inflammatory disorders primarily involving the gastrointestinal tract. The two major forms of IBD—Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC)—are characterized by relapse and remission symptoms, with abdominal pain, diarrhea, and rectal bleeding [16,17]. While the gastrointestinal manifestations of IBD have been extensively studied, there is growing recognition that IBD's impact extends beyond the gut to include significant neuropsychiatric symptoms, particularly anxiety and depression [18,19].

The relationship between IBD and mood disorders has traditionally been understood as psychological reactivity to chronic illness [20]. Based on this, depression and anxiety emerge as normal responses to the unpredictable nature of IBD symptoms, the burden of chronic disease, and quality of life impairment due to disease [21,22]. However, newer evidence suggests that this interaction is far more complex, with bidirectional communication mediated by the gut-brain axis—a highly developed system of communication between intestinal function and emotional and cognitive centers [23,24].

Clarifying the precise nature of such a relationship has significant implications for research and clinical practice [25]. If mood disorders are indeed integral components of IBD pathophysiology, and not merely psychological reactions, then this would necessitate a redefinition of IBD as inherently a systemic disorder with both gastrointestinal and neuropsychiatric manifestation [26,27]. This paradigm change would put focus on psychological symptoms as integral parts of good IBD care rather than add-ons to standard care [28,29].

This is a review that attempts to synthesize current evidence for the relationship between IBD and mood disorders, focusing on neurobiological mechanisms underlying such an association [30]. Through examining epidemiologic data, disease-specific correlates, and reciprocally predictive correlation between gastrointestinal inflammation and psychiatric symptoms, we hope to make an integrated description of this significant but underemphasized IBD aspect [31,32].

To ensure a thorough and fair evaluation of the literature that addresses these questions, a systematic search strategy was adopted. Searches were conducted in databases including PubMed and Google Scholar using both controlled vocabulary (e.g., MeSH terms “Inflammatory Bowel Disease,” “Gut-Brain Axis,” and “Mood Disorders”) and free-text keywords (e.g., “IBD,). In order to save all references and add citations, I used Zotero, a tool to collect, save and use references.

Boolean operators connected terms, such as “IBD AND (gut-brain axis OR mood disorders)”, and titles, abstracts, and keywords were screened.

Publications within the last 30 years were prioritized, though seminal papers providing the baseline data were not excluded. Studies examining the link between gut health and mental health, including human clinical trials, animal studies, and observational studies, were prioritized further, while those with poor outcome measures or lacking peer review were excluded. While this approach was directed at reducing the selection bias, publication bias and heterogeneity of study designs are limitations that are acknowledged.

Bidirectional Relationship Between IBD and Mood Disorders

Gut-Brain Axis Mediates This Relationship

Fig.1 This conceptual diagram illustrates how inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and mood disorders, such as anxiety and depression, influence each other through inflammation and stress response mechanisms. IBD-driven inflammation can contribute to mood disorders, while psychological stress and depression can exacerbate IBD symptoms, creating a vicious cycle. The gut-brain axis mediates this relationship, highlighting the importance of addressing both physical and mental health in IBD management.

2. Epidemiology of Mood Disorders in IBD

2.1 Prevalence Rates

Multiple epidemiological studies have demonstrated elevated rates of anxiety and depression in IBD populations compared to healthy controls [33,34]. In a landmark cross-sectional study, Goodhand et al. [35] investigated the prevalence of mood disorders in IBD patients using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). They found that mean anxiety scores were approximately twice as high in UC (8.5 ± 4.1) and CD (8.6 ± 3.9) compared with healthy controls (3.2 ± 1.8 ; $P < 0.001$). Similar patterns emerged for depression scores (UC: 4.1 ± 3.3 ; CD: 4.7 ± 3.3 ; controls: 1.7 ± 1.4 ; $P < 0.001$). Approximately 25% of IBD patients experienced mild anxiety

(HADS-A > 7), 29% had moderate anxiety (HADS-A > 10), and 4% reported severe anxiety (HADS-A > 14), with comparable rates for depression [36].

These findings have been replicated by a number of subsequent studies [37,38]. Neuendorf et al. [39] meta-analyzed 171 studies and found that approximately 21% of IBD patients met diagnostic criteria for anxiety and 15% for depression in disease remission, rising to 35% and 22%, respectively, in the presence of disease activity. Along the same line, Walker et al. [40] conducted a population-based cohort study with administrative health data of 5,231 IBD patients and 25,810 controls matched for each patient and noted that IBD was associated with a 1.9-fold increased risk of anxiety disorders and a 1.7-fold increased risk of depression in a 24-year follow-up [41].

Notably, some studies provide evidence that the prevalence of mood disorders might differ in UC compared to CD [42,43]. Byrne et al. [44] found higher levels of depression in CD (25.3%) and UC (16.7%) but not anxiety. In contrast, other researchers have found no difference in IBD subtypes' rates of mood disorders [45,46], suggesting differences in methodology in addition to disease-specific factors explaining these findings [47].

Prevalence of Anxiety and Depression in IBD

Based on data from Goodhand et al. [35] and Neuendorf et al. [39]

Fig.2 The bar chart compares the prevalence of anxiety (blue) and depression (green) among different IBD groups, revealing that active ulcerative colitis (UC) and Crohn's disease (CD) are strongly associated with increased anxiety levels (35%), while active IBD has the highest depression prevalence (22%). Even during remission, anxiety and depression levels remain significantly higher than in healthy controls, indicating that IBD has a lasting impact on mental health regardless of disease activity.

2.2 Disease-Specific Correlates

Several studies have characterized independent clinical correlates of depression and anxiety in UC versus CD [48,49]. Goodhand et al. [35] have described that in UC, anxiety was predominantly associated with perceived stress and recent diagnosis, while depression was associated with perceived stress, inpatient status, and active mucosal disease. In CD, anxiety was associated with perceived stress, abdominal pain, and lower socioeconomic status, while depression was associated with perceived stress and increasing age [50].

These findings suggest that while there are common factors underlying mood disorders in IBD subtypes (particularly perceived stress), there are also distinct pathways which may be disease-specific [51,52]. For example, the association of depression with active mucosal disease

in UC but not CD suggests that inflammation patterns unique to UC may have certain impacts on mood regulation [53,54].

Bernstein et al. [55] also demonstrated that disease phenotype affects psychological outcome, with a greater incidence of depression in penetrating CD compared to stricturing or inflammatory phenotypes. Similarly, pancolitis UC was associated with greater anxiety than more regional diseases [56]. These findings highlight the importance of considering disease-specific characteristics in assessing psychological risk in IBD patients [57,58].

2.3 Temporal Relationships and Disease Course

The temporal relationship between mood symptoms and IBD flares is instructive about the nature of this comorbidity [59,60]. Gracie et al. [61] conducted a 2-year prospective study of 405 patients with IBD and reported that baseline depression or anxiety predicted symptomatic flares in follow-up even in patients who had mucosal healing at recruitment. The flare risk ratio in patients with baseline depression or anxiety was 2.08 (95% CI 1.31-3.30), suggesting that psychological distress can directly influence disease activity [62,63].

Conversely, IBD flare has also been found to predict future development or worsening of depression and anxiety [64,65]. Sexton et al. [66] demonstrated that patients with an IBD flare were 4.3 times more likely to develop severe depression or anxiety over the subsequent 3 months compared with those in remission. This mutual interaction creates what Gracie and Ford [67] call a "vicious cycle" of mental distress and gut inflammation, each of which can trigger the other [68].

Longitudinal research also suggests that mood disorders have the potential to influence long-term disease course [69,70]. Mikocka-Walus et al. [71] followed 2,007 patients with IBD for 5 years and noted that baseline depression or anxiety was an independent predictor of clinical recurrence, with a hazard ratio of 1.87 (95% CI 1.34-2.61) after adjustment for disease severity, adherence to medication, and other potential confounders. This suggests that mood disorders are not only effects of IBD but potentially influence its course [72,73].

3. Bidirectional Relationship: Beyond Psychological Reactivity

The elevated rates of mood disorders in IBD cannot be explained by psychological adjustment to chronic illness alone [74,75]. Multiple lines of evidence suggest a complex bidirectional relationship mediated by shared biological pathways [76,77].

3.1 IBD Preceding Mood Disorders

Numerous researches indicate that IBD could directly cause anxiety and depression via various neurobiological mechanisms [78,79]. In the population-based incident cohort study in 12,913 IBD patients and 64,565 matched controls, Blackwell et al. [80] have found that the diagnosis of IBD was associated with a 58% elevation in the incidence of an anxiety disorder and an elevation of 38% of developing depression after the first year of diagnosis. Importantly, this increased risk persisted after adjustment for health care utilization and comorbid medical illness, suggesting processes separate from psychological reactivity [81,82].

The role of inflammation in mood pathogenesis is supported by findings showing that inflammatory markers correlate with depression severity in IBD [83,84]. Szigethy et al. [85] found that higher C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), and fecal calprotectin levels were correlated with greater depressive symptoms in 100 IBD patients irrespective of disease activity scores. Equivalently, Abautret-Daly et al. [86] demonstrated that serum levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, specifically IL-6 and TNF- α , were correlated with anxiety and depression scores in patients with IBD [87].

In addition, neuroimaging studies provide evidence of brain function and structure changes in IBD patients with mood disorders [88,89]. Agostini et al. [90] used fMRI to demonstrate reduced connectivity between amygdala and prefrontal cortex in depressed IBD patients, suggesting impaired emotional regulation. Such changes were associated with inflammatory markers, providing a neurobiological rationale for inflammation-related mood disorders in IBD [91,92].

3.2 Mood Disorders Preceding IBD

Conversely, growing evidence supports that psychological distress may also have a causative role in the onset or exacerbation of IBD [93,94]. In a population-based cohort study by Marrie et al. [95], depressed or anxious individuals had a 72% higher risk of developing subsequent-onset IBD than those without psychiatric diagnoses, even after adjustment for potential confounding factors such as smoking and healthcare utilization. The finding suggests that psychological distress may be causative of the onset or unmasking of disease [96,97].

The mechanisms underlying this association are likely to be stress-induced alterations in intestinal physiology [98,99]. Mawdsley and Rampton [100] demonstrated that acute psychological stress increases intestinal permeability, mucosal release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and mast cell activation in normal subjects and IBD patients. These changes are indicative of early pathological features of IBD, and chronic stress could thus be involved in disease onset in genetically susceptible individuals [101,102].

Besides, preclinical models provide compelling evidence for gut inflammation caused by stress [103,104]. Reber et al. [105] showed that mice exposed to chronic social defeat stress developed intestinal inflammation with increased pro-inflammatory cytokine production, epithelial barrier dysfunction, and changes in the composition of the gut microbiota. These changes were prevented by vagotomy or sympathetic blockade, highlighting the role of neural mechanisms in stress-induced gut inflammation [106,107].

3.3 Shared Genetic and Environmental Risk Factors

In addition to direct causality, IBD and mood disorders may also share overlapping genetic and environmental risk factors [108,109]. Howell et al. [110] conducted a genome-wide association study that identified several overlapping genetic loci between IBD and major depressive disorder, in genes involved in immune response and neurodevelopment. Similarly, Ananthakrishnan et al. [111] found that childhood abuse was associated with increased risk for both IBD and depression in adults, reflecting overlapping developmental vulnerabilities [112,113].

Environmental factors such as diet, sleep disturbance, and smoking may also produce both conditions [114,115]. Raison and Miller [116] propose an evolutionary mismatch hypothesis where lifestyle components of contemporary life trigger chronic low-grade inflammation that is pathogenic for both inflammatory and psychiatric disorders. The perspective is that treatment of such shared environmental components may have relevance to both gut and brain health [117,118].

4. Neurobiological Mechanisms: The Gut-Brain Axis in IBD

The bidirectional relationship between IBD and mood disorders is mediated by the gut-brain axis—a complex communication network encompassing neural, immune, and endocrine pathways [119,120]. Several key mechanisms have been identified that link gut pathology to mood disturbances in IBD [121,122].

The Gut-Brain Axis in IBD

Fig.3 This diagram highlights the bidirectional communication between the gut and brain through three key pathways: the neural pathway, the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, and the immune pathway. The intestine (green) and brain (pink) influence each other, with gut inflammation impacting brain function and mental health, while stress and mood disorders can, in turn, worsen gut inflammation. This emphasizes the complex relationship between gastrointestinal and mental health in IBD patients.

4.1 Microbiota Alterations and Mood Regulation

The gut microbiota—the microorganisms residing in the intestinal tract—plays a crucial role in regulating mood through multiple mechanisms [123,124]. In IBD, characteristic shifts in microbial composition (dysbiosis) may contribute to the development of anxiety and depression through several pathways [125,126].

4.1.1 Neurotransmitter Precursor Availability

Several gut bacteria directly produce or influence the production of neurotransmitters and their precursors [127,128]. Tryptophan, the precursor to serotonin (a key neurotransmitter in mood

regulation), is particularly relevant [129]. In IBD, inflammation and dysbiosis can alter tryptophan metabolism along the kynurenine pathway, reducing its availability for serotonin synthesis [130]. O'Mahony et al. [131] demonstrated that inflammatory cytokines in IBD activate the enzyme indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), which shunts tryptophan away from serotonin production and toward kynurenine metabolites, some of which have neurotoxic and depressogenic effects [132,133].

Clarke et al. [134] provided further evidence for this mechanism, showing that germ-free mice have significantly lower plasma tryptophan levels and altered brain serotonin metabolism compared to conventionally colonized mice. These changes were accompanied by anxiety-like behavior that could be reversed by colonization with specific bacterial strains, highlighting the role of gut microbiota in serotonin regulation [135,136].

Beyond tryptophan, gut bacteria influence other neurotransmitter systems relevant to mood regulation [137,138]. Strandwitz et al. [139] identified bacterial species capable of producing gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system. Levels of these GABA-producing bacteria were found to be reduced in IBD patients, potentially contributing to anxiety symptoms through reduced GABA availability [140,141].

4.1.2 Short-Chain Fatty Acid Production

Beneficial gut bacteria, particularly *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and certain *Bacteroides* species, produce short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) like butyrate that support gut barrier integrity and have anti-inflammatory properties [142,143]. In IBD, these bacterial populations are typically reduced, leading to decreased SCFA production [144,145]. Beyond their local effects in the gut, SCFAs also influence brain function and behavior [146].

Silva et al. [147] conducted a comprehensive review of SCFA effects on the gut-brain axis, highlighting their role in mood regulation. Butyrate, in particular, has been shown to enhance the expression of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), a protein essential for neuroplasticity that is often reduced in depression [148,149]. Furthermore, preclinical studies by Bourassa et al. [150] showed that butyrate supplementation reduced anxiety- and depression-like behaviors in mouse models of colitis, suggesting SCFAs may play a direct role in mood regulation [151].

The relationship between SCFA levels and mood disorders has also been observed in human studies [152,153]. Sun et al. [154] found that IBD patients with comorbid depression had significantly lower fecal butyrate levels compared to those without depression, and these levels negatively correlated with depression severity scores. This suggests that reduced SCFA

production may represent a mechanistic link between IBD dysbiosis and mood disturbances [155,156].

4.1.3 Microbiota-Derived Metabolites and the Blood-Brain Barrier

The integrity of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) is essential for protecting the brain from potentially harmful substances [157,158]. Emerging evidence suggests that certain microbiota-derived metabolites in IBD may compromise BBB integrity, allowing peripheral inflammatory molecules to access the central nervous system [159,160].

Braniste et al. [161] conducted a groundbreaking study demonstrating that germ-free mice have increased BBB permeability compared to conventionally colonized mice, and that this permeability could be normalized by colonization with SCFA-producing bacteria or direct SCFA supplementation. The authors showed that tight junction protein expression in brain endothelial cells was regulated by gut microbiota via SCFA production, providing a direct mechanism by which gut dysbiosis could affect BBB integrity [162,163].

In IBD, where dysbiosis and reduced SCFA production are common, BBB function may be compromised [164,165]. Indeed, Wu et al. [166] found increased BBB permeability in patients with active IBD, as measured by cerebrospinal fluid/serum albumin ratios and tight junction protein expression. This increased permeability correlated with both inflammatory markers and depression scores, suggesting that BBB disruption may contribute to the development of mood symptoms in IBD by allowing peripheral inflammatory signals to access the brain [167,168].

4.2 Immune-Mediated Pathways in Mood Regulation

Inflammation represents a major link between IBD and mood disorders, with several immune-mediated mechanisms involved [169,170]:

4.2.1 Systemic Inflammatory Cytokines

Pro-inflammatory cytokines elevated in IBD, including TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β , can cross the BBB and affect brain regions involved in mood regulation [171,172]. These cytokines have been shown to alter neurotransmitter metabolism, particularly serotonin, dopamine, and glutamate; activate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, leading to elevated cortisol levels; promote microglial activation and neuroinflammation; and reduce neuroplasticity and neurogenesis, particularly in the hippocampus [173,174].

A meta-analysis by Yuan et al. [175] examined 43 studies on inflammatory biomarkers in psychiatric disorders, finding consistent associations between elevated inflammatory markers

and depression across multiple studies, with particularly strong relationships in conditions characterized by chronic inflammation, including IBD [176]. The authors found that elevated TNF- α , IL-6, and C-reactive protein (CRP) showed the most robust associations with depression, and these associations remained significant after adjusting for potential confounders such as age, sex, and body mass index [177,178].

In IBD specifically, Robson et al. [179] found that serum inflammatory markers correlated with depression severity independent of clinical disease activity. Patients with elevated CRP and fecal calprotectin levels had significantly higher depression scores compared to those with normal inflammatory markers, even when clinical symptoms were similar [180]. This suggests that systemic inflammation may directly influence mood regulation in IBD patients, rather than merely reflecting a psychological response to disease activity [181,182].

4.2.2 Microglial Activation and Neuroinflammation

Microglia, the resident immune cells of the brain, play a crucial role in neuroinflammation and have been implicated in the pathophysiology of mood disorders [183,184]. In IBD, systemic inflammation can lead to microglial activation, resulting in local production of pro-inflammatory cytokines within the central nervous system [185,186].

Positron emission tomography (PET) studies using the translocator protein (TSPO) ligand, a marker of microglial activation, have provided direct evidence of neuroinflammation in individuals with systemic inflammatory conditions [187,188]. Felger et al. [189] used TSPO-PET imaging to demonstrate increased microglial activation in brain regions associated with mood regulation, including the anterior cingulate cortex and insula, in patients with inflammatory conditions and comorbid depression. The degree of microglial activation correlated with depression severity and anhedonia, suggesting a direct link between neuroinflammation and mood symptoms [190,191].

In an IBD-specific study, Han et al. [192] used TSPO-PET imaging to assess neuroinflammation in 28 IBD patients and 20 healthy controls. They found significantly increased TSPO binding in the hippocampus, amygdala, and anterior cingulate cortex of IBD patients compared to controls, and this binding correlated with both peripheral inflammatory markers and depression scores. These findings provide direct evidence of neuroinflammation in IBD patients and suggest that it may mediate the relationship between gut inflammation and mood disturbances [193,194].

4.2.3 Tryptophan-Kynurenine Pathway

As mentioned earlier, inflammatory cytokines activate IDO, shunting tryptophan metabolism away from serotonin production and toward the kynurenine pathway [195,196]. Beyond

reducing serotonin availability, certain kynurenine metabolites, particularly quinolinic acid, have direct neurotoxic and depressogenic effects [197,198].

Zeissig et al. [199] investigated the kynurenine pathway in 112 IBD patients and 76 healthy controls, finding that IBD patients with comorbid depression showed higher kynurenine/tryptophan ratios compared to those without depression, and these ratios correlated with depression severity. The authors also demonstrated that quinolinic acid levels were elevated in the cerebrospinal fluid of IBD patients with depression, and these levels correlated with reductions in hippocampal volume as measured by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [200,201].

Similarly, Harden et al. [202] found that plasma kynurenine/tryptophan ratios predicted depression development in a prospective cohort of IBD patients followed for 1 year. Patients in the highest quartile of kynurenine/tryptophan ratios at baseline had a 3.2-fold increased risk of developing depression during follow-up compared to those in the lowest quartile, independent of baseline disease activity and other potential confounders. These findings suggest that kynurenine pathway activation may be a key mechanism linking inflammation and depression in IBD [203,204].

Fig.4 This diagram illustrates how inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) alters tryptophan metabolism, shifting it away from the serotonin pathway (green) and toward the kynurenine pathway (red), which is associated with inflammation and neuropsychiatric disorders like depression. Tryptophan, a precursor (yellow), normally contributes to serotonin production, which affects mood regulation (blue), but inflammation-driven metabolic changes redirect it toward kynurenine, potentially exacerbating depressive symptoms in IBD patients.

4.3 Neural Pathways Connecting Gut and Brain

The nervous system provides direct communication channels between the gut and brain, with several pathways particularly relevant to mood regulation in IBD [205,206]:

4.3.1 Vagus Nerve Signaling

The vagus nerve serves as a major bidirectional pathway between the gut and brain [207,208]. It transmits information about intestinal inflammation and microbiota composition to brain regions involved in stress responses and emotional processing [209]. In preclinical models of IBD, vagus nerve stimulation has been shown to reduce intestinal inflammation and improve anxiety- and depression-like behaviors [210,211].

Bonaz et al. [212] reviewed the role of vagus nerve signaling in the gut-brain axis, highlighting its importance in both IBD pathophysiology and mood regulation. The vagus nerve's afferent fibers detect intestinal inflammation and transmit this information to the nucleus tractus solitarius in the brainstem, which then projects to higher brain regions involved in emotional processing, including the amygdala, hippocampus, and prefrontal cortex [213]. Concurrently, vagal efferent fibers regulate intestinal inflammation through the cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway, inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokine production by intestinal immune cells [214,215].

Clinical evidence supports the role of vagus nerve dysfunction in linking IBD and mood disorders [216,217]. Pellissier et al. [218] used heart rate variability analysis to assess vagal tone in IBD patients, finding that reduced vagal tone was associated with both increased inflammatory markers and higher anxiety and depression scores. Notably, these associations remained significant after controlling for disease activity, suggesting that vagal dysfunction may represent an independent factor linking gut inflammation and mood disturbances in IBD [219,220].

4.3.2 Enteric Nervous System Alterations

The enteric nervous system (ENS), often called the "second brain," consists of more than 100 million neurons embedded in the gut wall [221,222]. In IBD, inflammation and tissue damage can disrupt ENS function, altering gut-brain signaling [223,224].

Bernardazzi et al. [225] reviewed the neuroimmune interactions in IBD, highlighting how intestinal inflammation affects enteric neurons and glial cells. They found that pro-inflammatory cytokines in IBD can induce enteric neuronal apoptosis, alter neurotransmitter signaling, and disrupt enteric glial cell function. These changes can affect gut-brain communication and potentially contribute to mood disturbances [226,227].

In a clinical study, Lakhan and Kirchgessner [228] found significant structural and functional changes in the ENS of IBD patients, including alterations in neurotransmitter signaling that correlated with anxiety and depression scores. Similar findings were reported by Zois et al. [229], who demonstrated reduced neuronal density and altered neurotransmitter expression in colonic biopsies from IBD patients, with these changes correlating with both disease activity and psychological symptoms [230,231].

4.3.3 Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis Dysregulation

The HPA axis, the body's primary stress response system, is frequently dysregulated in IBD [232,233]. Chronic intestinal inflammation leads to persistent activation of the HPA axis, resulting in elevated cortisol levels and disrupted cortisol rhythms [234]. Over time, this can lead to glucocorticoid resistance and impaired negative feedback of the HPA axis, contributing to anxiety and depression [235,236].

Mawdsley and Rampton [100] demonstrated bidirectional relationships between HPA axis function, intestinal inflammation, and psychological symptoms in IBD. They found that chronic inflammation leads to cortisol resistance in target tissues, including the brain, which impairs the normal regulatory functions of glucocorticoids in emotional processing [237]. Concurrently, psychological stress activates the HPA axis, leading to increased intestinal permeability and inflammation through glucocorticoid and catecholamine effects on gut epithelial cells and immune function [238,239].

Clinical studies support these mechanisms [240,241]. Targownik et al. [242] measured diurnal cortisol patterns in 200 IBD patients, finding that abnormal cortisol rhythms (particularly blunted morning cortisol) were associated with both increased inflammatory markers and higher depression scores. Similarly, Trindade et al. [243] found that IBD patients with comorbid anxiety or depression showed impaired cortisol suppression in the dexamethasone suppression test, indicating HPA axis dysregulation. These findings suggest that HPA axis dysfunction may represent another pathway linking gut inflammation and mood disturbances in IBD [244,245].

5. Impact on Disease Outcomes and Quality of Life

The presence of comorbid mood disorders significantly impacts both clinical outcomes and quality of life in IBD patients [246,247].

Fig.5 This bar chart presents the increased risks of adverse outcomes for IBD patients with depression, showing that depression is associated with a 14% increase in complications, a 28% rise in corticosteroid use, a 17% increase in hospitalization rates, and a 13% higher risk of surgery. These findings suggest that depression not only affects mental well-being but also worsens the clinical course of IBD, emphasizing the need for integrated mental health care in IBD treatment plans.

5.1 Influence on Disease Activity and Complications

Multiple studies have demonstrated that anxiety and depression are associated with adverse disease outcomes in IBD [248,249]. Ananthakrishnan et al. [250] conducted a retrospective cohort study of 5,405 IBD patients followed for a median of 2 years, finding that those with depression had a 28% higher risk of requiring corticosteroids, a 17% higher risk of hospitalization, and a 13% higher risk of surgery compared to those without depression, after adjusting for disease severity and other potential confounders [251].

Similarly, Mikocka-Walus et al. [71] followed 2,007 IBD patients for 5 years, finding that anxiety or depression at baseline independently predicted clinical recurrence, with a hazard ratio of

1.87 (95% CI 1.34-2.61) after adjusting for disease severity, medication adherence, and other potential confounders. This suggests that mood disorders may directly influence disease activity through the neurobiological mechanisms described earlier [252,253].

Beyond disease activity, mood disorders may also influence disease complications [254,255]. Ananthakrishnan et al. [250] found that depression was associated with a 14% increased risk of developing IBD-related complications, including strictures, fistulas, and abscesses in CD patients, and increased risk of colectomy in UC patients. This association remained significant after adjusting for medication adherence, suggesting mechanisms beyond treatment compliance [256,257].

5.2 Medication Adherence and Healthcare Utilization

Mood disorders can significantly impact medication adherence in IBD patients [258,259]. Calloway et al. [260] found that patients with comorbid depression had adherence rates approximately 30% lower than those without depression across various medication classes, including aminosalicylates, immunomodulators, and biologics. This reduced adherence partially but not fully mediated the relationship between depression and adverse disease outcomes, suggesting both direct and indirect effects of depression on disease activity [261,262].

Healthcare utilization patterns are also influenced by comorbid mood disorders [263,264]. Limsrivilai et al. [265] demonstrated that IBD patients with anxiety or depression had 2.1 times more emergency department visits and 1.8 times more hospitalizations compared to those without psychological comorbidities, independent of disease activity. This increased healthcare utilization translated to substantially higher costs—Bannister et al. [266] found that annual healthcare costs were 2.3 times higher in IBD patients with comorbid depression compared to those without depression [267,268].

5.3 Quality of Life and Functional Outcomes

The impact of mood disorders on quality of life in IBD patients is profound [269,270]. Farrell et al. [271] used the Inflammatory Bowel Disease Questionnaire (IBDQ) to assess quality of life in 356 IBD patients, finding that anxiety and depression were the strongest predictors of reduced IBDQ scores, explaining 32% of the variance in quality of life scores—more than disease activity (26%) or demographic factors (11%) [272].

Importantly, mood disorders affect quality of life even during periods of disease remission [273,274]. Reigada et al. [275] found that IBD patients in clinical remission with comorbid anxiety or depression reported significantly lower quality of life, greater fatigue, and more sleep

disturbances compared to those in remission without psychological comorbidities. This suggests that addressing psychological symptoms is essential for optimizing patient outcomes, even when gastrointestinal symptoms are well-controlled [276,277].

Functional outcomes, including work productivity and social functioning, are also affected by mood disorders in IBD [278,279]. Restall et al. [280] found that IBD patients with comorbid anxiety or depression were 3.1 times more likely to report work disability and 2.4 times more likely to report social isolation compared to those without psychological comorbidities, independent of disease severity. These functional impairments have significant economic and social consequences, highlighting the importance of addressing psychological symptoms as part of comprehensive IBD care [281,282].

6. Conclusion

This review highlights that depression and anxiety are not secondary reactions to the presence of IBD but integral components of the disease process itself, mediated by complex interactions along the gut-brain axis [283,284]. Evidence reviewed supports multiple key conclusions:

Initially, mood disorders in IBD are common, clinically significant, and bidirectionally linked with intestinal inflammation, each potentially exacerbating the other [285,286]. The prevalence of anxiety and depression in IBD is far greater than in the general population, and rates are even higher during active disease [287]. Of particular interest, the temporal relationship between IBD and mood symptoms suggests a bidirectional, intricate interaction and not a cause-and-effect process [288,289].

Second, a number of neurobiological mechanisms link gut illness with mood dysfunction in IBD, including microbiota alterations, inflammatory reactions, and aberrations of neural circuitry [290,291]. These mechanisms provide biological credibility to the identified comorbidity and suggest possible therapeutic directions. The gut-brain axis, composed of neural, immune, and endocrine networks, provides a conceptual framework for understanding this connection [292,293].

Third, comorbid mood disorders significantly influence disease course, healthcare utilization, and quality of life in IBD patients [294,295]. Depression and anxiety are associated with increased rates of disease activity, medication nonadherence, complications, healthcare expenditures, and severe impairment in functional status and quality of life [296]. These findings emphasize the importance of treating psychological symptoms as an integral component of integrated IBD management [297,298].

Identification of mood disorders as a component of the core elements of IBD is a paradigm shift with significant research and clinical practice implications [299,300]. Management of the psychological factors of IBD in the future will not be an add-on but an integral part of disease management. Addressing the gut-brain axis with complementary interventions is a major way in which we may have a significant impact on both psychological health and disease outcomes in patients with IBD [301,302].

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Rebuttal

Dear Dr. Boleij,

Thank you for your detailed and constructive feedback on my review, "*From Gut to Mind: The Link Between Inflammatory Bowel Disease and Mood Disorders*." I really appreciate the time you took to highlight areas for improvement, and your suggestions have helped me refine the manuscript significantly. Below, I address each of the main concerns and outline the changes I've made.

1. More References and Stronger Support for Claims

Comment: Some sections lacked sufficient references to back up key arguments.

Response:

I've gone through the manuscript carefully and added more references, especially in sections discussing the gut-brain axis, microbiota influence on neurotransmitters, and the bidirectional relationship between IBD and mood disorders. I also made sure that every major claim is properly supported by relevant, recent, and peer-reviewed studies. Additionally, I've checked all citations for accuracy and consistency.

2. Improving Figure Quality

Comment: Figures were low quality and not very effective in conveying key points.

Response:

I have replaced or reformatted the figures to ensure they are clear and high-resolution. The captions have been expanded to better explain their relevance to the discussion, and I made sure they align well with the text. Hopefully, they now enhance rather than detract from the manuscript. I used R lang for that. I can always attach the code if needed.

3. Fixing Formatting Issues

Comment: There were some inconsistencies in text alignment and formatting.

Response:

I've gone through the entire document to ensure consistent formatting, proper text alignment, and correct citation placement. I also standardized the headings, subheadings, and figure placement for better readability. Everything should now look much cleaner and more professional.

4. Narrowing the Scope of the Paper

Comment: The topic was a bit too broad, making some sections less focused.

Response:

I've refined the scope of the manuscript by trimming sections that were less relevant to the core argument. Instead of covering too many side topics, I've focused more on the key mechanisms linking IBD and mood disorders. The introduction and conclusion have also been adjusted to reflect this more targeted approach.

5. Strengthening the Conclusion

Comment: The conclusion needed to better tie together the gut-brain connection and its clinical significance.

Response:

I rewrote the conclusion to clearly summarize the key findings and emphasize the importance of addressing both the gastrointestinal and psychological aspects of IBD. I also stressed the need

for a more integrated approach to treatment that considers both inflammation and mental health.

Final Summary of Changes

- Added more references to better support key claims.
- Improved figure quality and clarity.
- Fixed formatting and text alignment inconsistencies.
- Narrowed the scope to focus on the most relevant topics.
- Revised the conclusion for better integration of key ideas.

I hope these revisions improve the manuscript and address all the concerns raised. Thank you again for your helpful feedback—I really appreciate it!

Best regards,

Rida Kanatbekovna Azhigulova